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Executive Summary

Potentially adverse effects of MNP to the environment will automatically affect humans. Hence, T4.2 (and so D4.3) will integrate the information on human exposure (from WP2) and hazard (from WP3) with results obtained for environmental species (see T2.3 and T3.6). All relevant regulations as well as activities and projects from the nano-specific risk assessment mentioned in T4.1 will be used in T4.2 as well. The environmental part of the integrated RA strategy will cover all human health relevant environments (i.e. agricultural soils, water and ambient air) including both functional (e.g. soil respiration) and structural (e.g. species diversity) components (STAMI). Besides the safety of the environment, the integrated strategy will also enable early identification of MP/NP of high concern for further testing and will be open for read across of some aspects (e.g. in silico, in vitro results) of the human health strategy (cf. T4.1). In addition, the integrated RA strategy will take mixture exposure (particles and associated chemicals or adsorbed environmental contaminants) and mechanistic aspects into account. Robust modelling approaches will be used and IATAs developed (probabilistic material flow model (WP2) (ULEIDEN). In addition, 'plastic-specific' modifications needed for the current set of (OECD) guidelines will be recommended. Given the virtually infinite possible combinations of particle properties relevant for risks, grouping and read across approaches will be proposed for specific cases of low solubility, low toxicity polymeric materials (under consideration of results from the EU H2020 GRACIOUS project and in agreement with the ECHA document on the grouping of nanoforms (Appendix R.6-1) (ULEIDEN, UFZ). The results obtained in WP2 and WP3 including the Sb4N modelling, will be used to exemplify and validate the integrated human health and environmental risk assessment strategy (ULEIDEN).

1. Description of task

Our current understanding of the risk of nano- and microplastic particles for human health is incomplete and there is a need for a scientific strategy, supported by reliable and validated methodologies, to assess exposure and hazards associated to these materials for humans and their direct environment along their lifecycle. Such a strategy will be developed in PlasticsFatE focusing on consumer (food, drinks), occupational (air) and environmental (agricultural soils) risks in compliance with existing regulations and guidance. This strategy will be based on the results achieved in PlasticsFatE WP1-3 and WP5, in close cooperation with the other CUSP projects, and on research and innovation outside the projects concerning the development of safe and sustainable plastics.

Graphical abstract

2. Introduction to integrated approaches to testing and assessment (IATAs) in the context of microplastic risk assessment

According to the JRC, Integrated Approaches to Testing and Assessment (IATA) are flexible approaches for chemical safety assessment based on the integration and translation of the data derived from multiple methods and sources (https://joint-research-centre.ec.europa.eu/eu-reference-laboratory-alternatives-animal-testing-eurl-ecvam/alternative-methods-toxicity-testing/iata-integrated-approaches-testing-and-assessment_en). One major goal in PlasticsFatE is to foster the use of *in vitro* data for risk assessment, thereby reducing the need for animal testing. The OECD conducted in total 24 case studies on IATA development since 2015 (<https://www.oecd.org/chemicalsafety/risk-assessment/iata-integrated-approaches-to-testing-and-assessment.htm>). Basically, an IATA aims at integrating and combining the results from various methodologies and approaches ((Q)SAR, read-across, *in chemico* / *in silico*, *in vitro*, *ex vivo*, *in vivo* or omic technologies) to create a holistic understanding of the mechanisms underlying the hazard of a substance, and make this knowledge usable for regulatory decision making. The Adverse Outcome Pathway (AOP) concept can be applied as a framework to develop IATAs [1, 2]. Guidance on reporting for IATAs is available from the OECD [2, 3].

For engineered nanomaterials, IATAs were developed in order to characterise the hazard of these materials and allow a prediction of toxicity depending on their physical-chemical properties. Much work has been performed in the frame of the EU project GRACIOUS (<https://www.h2020gracious.eu/>) [4, 5]. Most work was dedicated to the development of IATAs related to human hazard, but also environmental hazard was considered [e.g. 6, 7-10]. Even though there are differences between micro and nanoscaled polymer particles and engineered nanomaterials, in terms of risk assessment there are also many parallels, in the sense that a case-by-case assessment of each material is not feasible and that each material comes in a variety of different modifications concerning e.g. size, shape or surface charge. Hence, the IATAs developed in GRACIOUS project for human and environmental hazard serve as the basis for our work within PlasticsFatE.

As described in D4.2, during the first project phase the extent of knowledge gaps for MNP became evident, and hence the scope for the IATAs was adapted. As advised by the members of the advisory board, it was accepted that the development of full IATAs for MNP is currently premature. However, as in D4.2, the available knowledge was structured to provide decision trees to support the later IATA development. The decision trees propose decision nodes based on hypotheses, however, currently it is not possible to link all decision nodes in a logical way, as information is missing. This is also underlined by the framework published by the PolyRisk project, which is part of the CUSP cluster [11]. The framework focusses on the inhalation exposure pathway. In line with our way of thinking it was concluded that it is not yet possible to provide full IATAs for MNP, and likewise the existing knowledge was organized in a framework and linked to existing AOPs. Other than in our decision trees, plastic associated chemicals only find marginal consideration.

Figure 1. Principle for developing an IATA as outlined in the Gracious project.

In addition to the decision trees to support IATA development presented in D4.2, and to consider human exposure and hazards from MNP and their associated chemicals related to the immediate environment, the focus of deliverable D4.3 is on water, occupational (air) and environment (agricultural soils) related risks.

In close collaboration with PlasticsFatE WP3, mechanistic information on nano as well as microplastic particle effects will be incorporated into the IATAs. Knowledge of particle physical-chemical characteristics that were identified as crucial for hazardous effects will be considered as well, together with the methods to detect them. Plastic associated chemicals comprise a large and in part unexplored group of substances, and are also considered here, mainly based on knowledge from the scientific literature, as few experiments on the effects of plastic-associated chemicals on environmental organisms have been conducted in the frame of PlasticsFatE.

2.1. Development of decision trees to support ITS and IATAs (focus on agricultural soil, water and ambient air)

Decision trees to support future IATA development related to human exposure pathways and health outcomes of plastic and microplastic exposure have been developed in Task 4.1. and presented in Deliverable 4.2. They are based on IATAs developed in the GRACIOUS project. Other outcome from this project were IATAs for aquatic systems, including the discussion of implications for grouping and read-across [12]. These IATAs serve as an entry point for the work related to this deliverable. Here, the focus lies on exposure to MNP and associated chemicals via agricultural soils, ambient air and water, with the aim to identify hotspots of exposure for human via environmental pathways, and the hazard associated to this.

According to [12], for aquatic ecotoxicity testing of engineered nanomaterials, 4 decision nodes were defined referring to:

- Dissolution
- Dispersion stability
- Chemical and biological transformations
- Toxicity ratio of solutes versus particles in the overall suspension

These decision nodes provide a good basis for assessing MNPs impact on aquatic organisms, but as for the human IATAs, modifications are needed due to the different chemistry and properties of MNPs.

For example, dissolution is not a relevant decision node for polymer particles. Dispersion stability has to include the fact that plastics particles may not only sink but also float. Chemical and biological transformations of microplastic particles occur, but for polymer materials, other mechanisms of aging and weathering need to be included. For the toxicity ratio of solutes to particles in the overall suspension, also adaptation to microplastic particles is warranted, considering the leaching of additives, unintentionally added chemicals as well as degradation products into test media.

In addition, the tiered testing strategy for each of the four decision nodes need refinement, as for MNP different methodology is used.

As the paper by Cross et al. (2023) focusses on aquatic environment, IATA development for this compartment for MNP has been prioritized. For the terrestrial and air compartment, further modifications will be necessary. Here, we will start with the careful formulation of hypotheses (composition, polymer type, size, shape determines impact, additives determine toxicity, size determines uptake in plants...). Emphasis will be given to include decision nodes on contaminants / effects of leachates, as this has already been identified as an important driver of toxicity for MNP. Further, we will provide recommendations for the methodology (e.g. characterization techniques) and the definition of threshold values, which are crucial for the subsequent establishment of grouping and read-across approaches for MNP.

All compartments considered here are of course interlinked (e.g. soil and aquatic via sediment and ground water, soil and atmosphere via atmospheric deposition). For the purpose of formulating hypotheses, however, we ignore these linkages and consider each compartment in an isolated manner.

Further, given the high degree of uncertainty in MNP toxicity testing (see 2.2.1), we will explore the option to use MNP-specific IATAs to define data needs & data gaps, as well as gaps in methodology. Decision trees to support IATA development are provided, meaning that sometimes nodes and hypotheses are formulated, but no hierarchy between them can be established, yet. This needs further knowledge and integration in the future.

2.2 Aquatic compartment (freshwater, marine)

The focus was set on the relevance of human exposure via aquatic and marine organisms (e.g. fish, seafood, algae) consumed by humans. The decision tree to support the development of IATAs shall hence not aim at estimating the risk for environmental organisms present in this compartment. In Table 1 we suggest decision nodes for MNP and associated hazard via the aquatic compartment.

Table 1. Suggested decision nodes for MNP and associated chemicals hazard via the aquatic compartment (incl. marine).

Aquatic compartment (freshwater and marine), potential decision nodes and hypotheses, hierarchy may need adoption		
Decision node	(Sub) Hypothesis	Considerations / methods / trigger values
(1) Uptake is size dependent Accumulation of MNPs in the food basket depends on the amounts of MNPs adsorbed to food items and contained in the food matrix. Size determines the amount of MNPs within food.	Aquatic 1 Following consumption by humans of biota exposed in the aquatic environment, ingestion and subsequent internalization is driven by the size of the MNP particles.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Smaller MNPs hypothesized to be able to more easily pass cellular barriers. • Collect data on internalized MNPs of different size for specific biota relevant for the food basket. • Note: often co-variance of size with other particle properties.
(2) Internalization is shape (morphology) dependent	Aquatic 2 Following consumption by humans of biota exposed in the aquatic environment, internalization is driven by the morphology of the MNP particles.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Effective surface area or volume hypothesized to affect uptake. • Additional factors like surface charge and elasticity might also affect internalization. • Collect data on internalized MNPs of different morphologies for specific biota relevant for the food basket.
(3) Internalization depends on MNP composition	Aquatic 3 Following consumption by humans of biota exposed in the aquatic environment, internalization is driven by the composition of the MNP particles.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • MNP composition hypothesized to affect uptake. • Additional factors like size, surface charge and elasticity might also affect internalization. • Collect data on internalized MNPs of different composition for specific biota relevant for the food basket.
(4) Release of additives in biota affects their uptake by humans Additives might be released in the human body following uptake of MNPs and subsequent leaching of the additives. However, additives might also be released in the biota consumed and subsequently be more bioavailable in the human body.	Aquatic 4 Additives present in MNPs and released in food items that are part of the human food basket, are hypothesized to be more bioavailable for humans.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Distinguish release of additives in the human body and in the food items prior to consumption. • Consider residence time of MNPs in biota and in humans • Consider the composition of the gastrointestinal tract of food items and humans.

2.3 Agricultural soil

The focus was set on the relevance of human exposure via terrestrial organisms used for human food consumption (mainly crops). This mainly refers to uptake of MNP via the roots. The decision tree to support the development of IATAs shall hence not aim at estimating the risk for environmental organisms present in this compartment. There are indications that MNP presence in soils is also impacting soil properties (e.g. water holding capacity, pH, bulk soil density) which may pose a risk for agricultural plants, in particular through inducing drought [13]. Table 2 suggests decision nodes for MNP and associated hazard via the terrestrial compartment.

Table 2. Suggested decision nodes for MNP and associated chemicals hazard via the terrestrial compartment (incl. pore water).

Terrestrial compartment (soil, pore water), potential decision nodes and hypotheses, hierarchy may need adoption		
Decision node	(Sub) Hypothesis	Considerations / methods / trigger values
(1) Particle – soil interactions: adsorption, distribution, mobility	Soil 1 Following exposure via soil, lethal and sub-lethal toxicity to plants is driven by the fate of the MNP particles and its consequences for particles uptake by organisms.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Impacts uptake by soil organisms • Assess mobility in different types of soils (sand, clay...) • Assess fraction of particles in pore water (affects organism exposure)
(2) Chemical and biological transformations of soil MNP particles change soil environment (structure, pH, nutrients, DOC, water retention and holding capacity)	<p>Soil 2 MNP <u>persistence</u> impacts soil structure and water holding capacity: Following terrestrial exposure lethal and sub-lethal toxicity to representative terrestrial species is driven by the fate and toxicity characteristics of the MNP</p> <p>Soil 3 MNP <u>degradation</u> impacts pH, nutrient, additive and DOC content: Following terrestrial exposure lethal and sub-lethal toxicity to representative terrestrial species is driven by speed of degradation and soil properties.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Assess degradation, consider biodegradable plastic • Particle size changes over time (relevance for toxicity unknown, but assumption that more particles are taken up) • Corona formation • Assess soil properties to check for proper condition for organisms (pH, moisture...) • More additives are released
(3) Toxicity ratio of leachates versus particles in the soil	<p>Soil 4 Following terrestrial exposure lethal and sub-lethal toxicity to representative terrestrial species is driven by <u>MNP</u></p> <p>Soil 5 Following terrestrial exposure lethal and sub-lethal toxicity to representative terrestrial species is driven by <u>leachates</u></p> <p>Soil 6 Following terrestrial exposure lethal and sub-lethal toxicity to representative terrestrial species by <u>particle – leachate mixtures</u></p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Toxicity ratio shows the relevance of particles and leachates for overall toxicity • Consider residence time of MNP in soil for leaching

2.4 Ambient air, atmosphere

The focus was set on the relevance of human exposure via other organisms exposed to the atmosphere [14, 15], which is much more difficult considering the wide diversity (plants, insects, mammals, birds, etc.).

Again, we focused on organisms used for human food consumption, e.g. via crops whose upper parts collect MNP via atmospheric deposition. Further, this includes lung-breathing farm animals reared for human consumption. But also insects may play role, as they are increasingly used for human consumption. Farm animals might in addition be exposed via food containing MNP from atmospheric deposition (Table 3). The decision tree to support the development of IATAs shall hence not aim at estimating the risk for environmental organisms present in this compartment.

Table 3. Suggested decision nodes for MNP and associated chemicals hazard via the atmospheric compartment (airborne exposure).

Atmospheric compartment, potential decision nodes and hypotheses, hierarchy may need adoption		
Decision node	(Sub) Hypothesis	Considerations / methods / trigger values
(1) Particle – air interactions: adsorption, distribution, mobility	Atmo 1 Following exposure via air, lethal and sub-lethal toxicity to representative species is driven by the fate of the MNP particles and the consequences for particle uptake by organisms. Atmo 2 MNP may impact processes in the atmosphere (e.g. provision of condensation nuclei [16])	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Impacts uptake by organisms • Assess ability of MNPs to reach parts of the organisms used for human consumption • Associated chemicals: unknown if leaching of substances is a relevant pathway in air
(2) Chemical and biological transformations of MNP MNP particle properties change in air (e.g. UV-mediated aging)	Atmo 3 MNP chemical transformation impacts particle properties: Following atmospheric exposure lethal and sub-lethal toxicity to representative species is driven by the fate and toxicity characteristics of the MNP. Atmo 4 MNP biological transformation impacts particle properties: Following atmospheric exposure lethal and sub-lethal toxicity to representative species is driven by the fate and toxicity characteristics of the MNP.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Assess aging and weathering and subsequent changes in MNP properties • Particle size may change over time (relevance for toxicity unknown, but assumption that more particles are taken up by organisms) • Adsorption of contaminants • Corona formation relevant process? • Associated chemicals: unknown impact of transformation processes on leaching of substances
(3) Toxicity ratio of leachates versus particles	Atmo 5 Following air-borne exposure, lethal and sub-lethal toxicity to representative species is driven by <u>MNP</u> Atmo 5 Following air-borne exposure, lethal and sub-lethal toxicity to representative species is driven by <u>leachates</u> Atmo 7 Following air-borne exposure, lethal and sub-lethal toxicity to representative species by <u>particle – leachate mixtures</u>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Toxicity ratio shows the relevance of particles and leachates for overall toxicity • Relevance of leaching unknown in this compartment, residence time will impact the amount of substances released

2.5. Exposure and Hazard assessment in PlasticsFatE: What did we learn?

2.5.1. Modifications in OECD guidelines for MNP testing

OECD test guidelines initially developed for the testing of chemicals may require specifications and modifications for MNP. As experienced with the testing of engineered nanomaterials, particulate test items (as MNP are) behave differently in liquid media, as they do not dissolve but form dispersions of differing stability. Hence, modifications and guidance documents for nanomaterials are taken as a basis to suggest modification of existing OECD test guidelines, supplemented by experiences with MNP testing by the PlasticsFatE partners. For engineered nanomaterials, OECD guidance documents are available [17-19], and three guidelines have been specifically drafted for engineered nanomaterials: TG 318 on dispersion stability [20], TG 106 on adsorption desorption of soil [21], and TG 312 on leaching in soil [22]; as well as for plastic [23].

According to the results obtained in PlasticsFatE and the current state of knowledge, the following issues for adaptation in OECD TGs or guidance documents specifically for MNP are suggested:

- Buoyancy of many polymer particles is impacting cell culture as well as aquatic ecotoxicity assays. Surfactants might be used, there are also studies demonstrating loss of buoyancy due to biofilm formation
- Guidance on testing of buoyant particles could suggest test systems, e.g. floating plants like Lemna [24, 25] or Azolla [26], to ensure contact of MNP and the test organisms
- Contamination of MNP with pollutants or microbial toxins was shown to impact toxicity and immunology related outcomes, hence testing and removal by appropriate methods prior to toxicity testing is suggested
- Terrestrial ecotoxicity tests: adjustment of water regime, pH... more details and recommendation in [27, see Table 2]
- Regarding the role of associated chemicals for MNP hazard, and as a first step towards harmonized guidelines, a Technical Rule for preparation and testing of plastic with defined additive content was prepared [28]
- The leaching protocol selection tool likewise provides a structured approach to leachate testing
- Contamination of MNP during life cycle with environmental pollutants needs characterization before (eco)toxicity testing
- Consideration of functional biomarkers in cell-based assays

2.5.2. Leaching protocol selection tool

Initially, a document was prepared by WP4 members to provide an overview of studies on leachates from MNP to members of WP2 and WP3. This working paper was circulated within the PlasticsFatE consortium and presented at the General Assembly in Valencia (March 2024). The goal was to provide a broad overview on experimental approaches to leachate testing. Within the PlasticsFatE consortium, a rationale for experimental testing of MNP and associated chemicals was discussed. Leaching of plastic-associated chemicals is an important issue that needs consideration in the hazard assessment (HA) of MNP. For HA, the identity as well as the quantity of chemicals released from the particles is needed. Typically, leaching experiments are conducted by soaking MNP in liquid for defined amounts of time under variation of further conditions such as stirring or exposure to UV light. In WP3, this topic was initiated by a case study on LDPE and the commercial additives Lubio and ZnO nanoparticles [29]. In summary, our analysis of current literature revealed a broad variation in leaching conditions not only regarding the choice of plastic materials, but also related to leaching time, medium and accelerating conditions such as UV-exposure (overview, Figure 2). Further, the chemical analysis of leachates requires the combination of various methods, as leachates contain a mixture of different substances (e.g. heavy metals).

Figure 2. Overview of leaching conditions found in the scientific literature (Figure generated in BioRender). The Figure was created for the DSS as described in D4.7.

Accordingly, it was decided in the consortium to focus on the characterization of effects of the plastic materials alone, before adding further complexity to the system. Within PlasticsFatE, the issue of leaching was only considered in an experimental case study involving LDPE and commercially available additives [29].

However, we decided to further develop our review into a protocol selection tool that can support the experimental testing of plastic leachates and hence supports in the generation of reliable exposure and hazard data for plastic associated chemicals in the future. The respective data and protocols will get integrated in the IATAs.

The full elaboration of the tool (which was not considered in the initial project plan, but the need for it became apparent during the project) and its implementation into the DSS was not possible during the project time and will be completed afterwards. A manuscript is under preparation [28].

2.5.3. PlasticsFatE WP3: implications of results obtained in cell-based assays for hazard assessment

In cooperation with WP3 partners, we discussed how the experimental results on hypothesis-driven hazard testing in various cell models selected according to the exposure routes for MNP, can be integrated into the decision trees to support IATA development. Detailed summaries of WP3 toxicity testing data can be found in D3.1 and D3.4. According to the various cell-based assay that have been conducted, none of the tested polymer particles caused acute toxicity (biomarkers of adverse effects, e.g. cell viability). For example, the WP3 results show that PS-Eu exposure does not induce acute cytotoxicity in these models, but it affects cell-specific functions like surfactant, mucin, and cytokine

production. This highlights the limitations of standard cytotoxicity tests and the need to investigate cell function-specific signalling pathways for risk assessment.

Accordingly, the initial hypotheses about e.g. polymer type or sizes impacting the toxicity, were rejected. Toxic effects were observed for MNP particles carrying contaminants, indicating an important role of pollutants sorbed by MNP for their toxicity.

However, it was observed that specific cell functions are modified by particles exposure (Figure 3). These functional biomarkers can be differentiated into biomarkers of cell-specific functions (e.g. immune parameters, surfactant production, mucus production), biomarkers of stress response (e.g. metabolic activity, antioxidant production) and biomarkers of exposure (e.g. cellular uptake). Overall, MNP were demonstrated to have impacts on diverse human cell models, which are not acutely toxic, but may indicate unknown consequences for chronic exposure scenarios.

Figure 3. Integration of functional, non-classical biomarkers in risk assessment strategies (Figure by Damjana Drobne, UL)

For non-acutely toxic substances such as MNP, conventional hazard and risk assessment approaches will fail, e.g. due to the use of effects values (EC50, NOEL) for the deduction of limit / threshold values and related management measures. Due to the absence of clear dose-response relationships for MNP such effect values cannot be deduced for MNP.

At the same time, the elucidation of modification of functional biomarkers by MNP offers alternative endpoints, which, however, need to be integrated into MNP RA strategies in the future. How this integration can be managed needs further elaboration and is considered in the roadmap as one priority area. Detailed knowledge on MNP functional biomarkers will provide insights into mechanisms and modes of action of MNP. Hence, it is also of relevance for the generation of MNP specific AOPs, for the establishment of grouping and read-across approaches for MNP, and for frameworks such as SSbD.

2.5.4. Adverse Outcome Pathways (AOP)

Figure 4: AOP concept [30] and role of PlasticsFatE data for establishing AOPs for MNP effects. PlasticsFatE results mainly address the identification of key events on cellular level, several of which have been identified. Several cell lines and specific biomarkers were studied, reported in detail in WP3 deliverables.

An AOP describes the action of a toxicant in the form of a sequential chain of causally linked events (Figure 4). It covers different levels of biological organization, ultimately showing an adverse health or ecotoxicological effect [2, 30, 31]. In PlasticsFatE WP2 and WP3, experimental results were generated that cover the molecular, cellular and tissue level. As molecular initiating event (MIE), the biophysical interaction of MNP with cells was proven (see D3.3), but most probably there are more MIEs for MNP.

Here, the example of PS effects on two cell lines is described in more detail. PS particles did not induce cell or barrier damage or ROS production in A549 and Calu-3 cells. However, they increased the activity of acidic organelles in alveolar cells. TEM and Raman microscopy revealed that PS-Eu are internalised by cells in a dose- and cell-dependent manner in both lung models. In ALI-grown A549 cells, they induced ultrastructural changes suggesting functional alteration of the surfactant production process. These data were confirmed by quantification of surfactant proteins (SP), which showed that the intracellular fraction of SP is significantly downregulated. Taken together, our results show that PS do not induce acute cytotoxicity in alveolar and bronchial models of A549 and Calu-3 cells. However, PS MNPs can target cell-specific functions such as surfactant or mucus production, further supporting the idea that particle cytotoxicity may develop after long-term exposure.

Based on these results, we describe particle internalization as the molecular initiating event (MIE), based on the biophysical interaction between cellular biocomponents (membranes) and internalized particles. Altered cell functionality, such as surfactant or mucus production and altered surface tension, can be considered key events (KEs). As this leads to reduced or altered gas exchange, it constitutes an adverse outcome pathway (AOP).

In the literature, the induction of oxidative stress by microplastic particles is frequently described (gastrointestinal tract [32], male reproductive toxicity [33]). In PlasticsFatE, several cell lines from different tissues have been studied (e.g. macrophages, airway and intestinal epithelial cells), and the response to MNP is clearly cell-dependant, and functional changes and general cell response to stress have been identified (see D3.4 for details). These are relevant for assessing effects of long-term exposure (see Figure 4). Further, PlasticsFatE covered airway tissues in murine instillation studies. The key events here were increased release of pro-inflammatory markers and Neutrophil infiltration. For the GIT, SIMGI simulator was used to assess changes in the gut secretome and microbiome. In the future, also the effects of the plastic associated chemicals need to find consideration in AOP development [34]. In PlasticsFatE it was proven that chemical contaminants adsorbed on MNP were taken up by the cells and were bioavailable (D3.3).

2.5.5. Use of PlasticsFatE data for the exposure and fate models developed in other WPs

According to the initial DOA, robust modelling approaches for MNP should be used and integrated into the IATAs, e.g. to model exposure concentrations. Namely, two models should have been developed in PlasticsFatE: Sb4N modelling and a probabilistic material flow model (WP2). However, due to time restrictions, no further work on these models was done. Instead, we planned to use predictions and forecasts of MNP emissions and exposure concentrations obtained in WP2 and 5 to predict MNP abundance in environmental compartments.

In the last phase of the project, we performed a cross-WP data use exercise involving all models that have been developed in PlasticsFatE, with exposure and hazard data obtained in the project (see Table 4). Basically, one question should be answered: Are the PlasticsFatE data usable to run the models and obtain MNP exposure, hazard and risk estimates? The following tools and models were assessed (Table 4):

- Prospective multi-criteria decision support system (PMDCS; Del. 4.5) (WP4)
- Fate model (WP2)
- Occupational exposure model (WP2)
- Physiology based pharmacokinetic (PBPK) model (WP2)

As summarized in Table 4, neither the fate, occupational, nor the PBPK model are applicable at the current stage of development. Full validation is pending for the fate model (within PlasticsFatE, no measurements of environmental concentrations of MNP in different compartments were performed, which would be needed to validate the model) as well as the PBPK model (has so far been tested with simulated data). For the occupational exposure model, the campaigns done in WP5 are not yet fully evaluated, and metric problems persist related to the conversion of mass-based and number-based measurements. As for the PMDCS, it is the most mature model and has been validated in two case studies. However, still, the toxicity and exposure data generated in PlasticsFatE have not been used to run the model. This is because the hazard module within the PMDCS considers generalized hazard ratings that have not been determined for the common polymers assessed in the PlasticsFatE project. In addition, as laid out in more detail in D4.5, the PMDCS results are still subject to a high degree of uncertainty due to poorly populated databases. The respective data and knowledge gaps have been considered for a manuscript addressing the data needs for risk assessment [35, "wish list paper"]. Further, in the frame of CUSP WG5, a cross-project study on the use of project data on PS is planned.

Table 4: Cross-WP data use exercise: can data from WP 1, 2, 3 and 5 be used to run the models and obtain improved risk estimates for MNP?

Model (PlasticsFatE WP)	Status	Data from PlasticsFatE
PMCDs (WP4)	Validated (by case studies)	Limited usability, as the requirements for the hazard classification needed for this go beyond the toxicity endpoints assessed in WP3
Fate model (WP2)	Not validated	Limited data concerning environmental concentrations and behaviour available, few outdoor campaigns in PlasticsFatE to add data (e.g. outdoor air samples from WP2/WP5 by UBT)
Occupational exposure model (WP2)	Campaigns / evaluation ongoing	Metric problems, adaptation of model (checked in case study in WP5)
PBPK model (WP2)	(Validated)	no blood / urine data (yet) available from PlasticsFatE, simulated data has been used for validation

In summary, this exercise demonstrated that the use of modelled data for human exposure and hazard assessment is premature. However, the models were integrated into the PlasticsFatE DSS (see D4.7 for more details).

3. Development of a roadmap for future MNP risk assessment

Overall, even after 4 years of intense research into the impact of MNP on human health, we are still far away from robust and reliable data and knowledge that will allow us to conduct RA for MNP. Accordingly, one focus of WP4 was to systematically collect and prioritize the data and knowledge gaps that we experienced during our work on RA strategies and likewise in the development of the PMCDs tool (T4.3). The results are presented in a manuscript [35, "wish list paper"] and summarize inputs from various workshops that have been conducted within the project or at CUSP level (see D6.8 for a summary, e.g. stakeholder workshop at Burg Windeck). However, prioritization for future MNP research is not straightforward. There is much work still needed in different research fields, which are closely interconnected, and knowledge gaps are still too deep (e.g. monitoring for human exposure can only be done if reliable analytical methods are available). An attempt is presented in the wish list manuscript in the form of a table, which is, however, not a roadmap in the strictest sense. A summary of the most important action points is provided below. We will further contribute to the overall CUSP roadmap that aims at synthesizing the outcomes and future research actions from all 5 projects within CUSP. We contributed to the development of the roadmap draft via CUSP working group 5 on risk assessment and extensively discussed the first draft during the CUSP final meeting in Brussels (February 2025). The CUSP roadmap will be finalised later in 2025.

A condensed version of the table from the manuscript of the "wish list paper" is presented in Table 5 and Figure 5, summarizing the most important data gaps related to MNP in 6 priority action points. The order of appearance follows the logic of presenting the most important data and methods gaps to be filled on top. This prioritization attempt will also inform the CUSP roadmap.

Prio 0: Exposure and hazard assessment for plastic associated chemicals (the exposure and hazard assessment of plastic-associated chemical alone be done in parallel to the other priority areas)

Prio 1: QA/QC for reliable measurement of environmental and human exposure, and uptake and internalisation by humans (tissues etc.) -> make analytical methods fit for MNP measurement

Prio 2: MNP material provision with various compositions and properties that are well characterized for toxicological testing and span the whole range from pristine, to relevant in consumer products, to environmentally realistic (aged, adsorbed pollutants & pathogens)

Prio 3: Appropriate control particles for toxicity testing based on outcome of Prio 2

Prio 4: Assessing the joint effects of MNP and associated chemicals

Prio 5: Use different types of functional biomarkers for detection of potential long-term effects of MNP

Table 5. Summary of priority areas for future MNP data generation

Knowledge and Data gaps	General and test material-related challenges	Strategy to overcome challenges & QA/QC aspect
Prio 0: Exposure and hazard assessment for plastic associated chemicals (incl. plastic additives)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Limited availability of hazard information on numerous plastic-associated chemicals • Types and concentrations of additives and residual chemicals from polymer synthesis are unknown • Metals are known as relevant in some additives of plastic products, e.g., colour pigments, but still not appropriately addressed in analysis 	<p>(testing of relevant plastic-associated chemicals can be done using established assays, established concept can be used for mixture assessment)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Prioritization of chemicals for hazard assessment according to specific criteria (e.g. production volume)
Prio 1: Quality assurance and quality control	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reliable and representative sampling and processing of samples • Limited availability of sample preparation methods (e.g., lower size limit or mass, low expected concentrations) • Homogeneity of samples • Determination of background values, particle changes and losses during sample processing • Prevention and monitoring of contamination of samples from surrounding environment • Precision and accuracy = trueness between labs, ILCs • Choice of unit (mass/number, weight/number) to compare results • QA/QC of analyses of MNPs in tissue samples • QA/QC of MNPs hazard testing 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Development of quality-assured methods and protocols for sample collection & preparation • Definition of minimum QA/QC standards • International standards • community agreed standards for QA/QC analyses of MNPs in tissue samples (control of contaminants; performance of instruments) • QA/QC of MNPs for hazard testing • (more details in D2.3 Report on QA/QC, see appendix)
Prio 2: MNP material provision with various compositions and properties	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Specific for internalization studies: Model MNPs that can be distinguished from background (e.g. labelled) • Producing human exposure relevant MNPs (consumer products) for testing • Environmentally relevant MNP for <i>in vitro</i> and <i>in vivo</i> testing • Consider aging (transformation and biodegradation) of MNPs • Consider nanoplastics for testing • Suitable reference materials 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Develop particle-based analytical methods with LOD below particle sizes (and concentrations) likely for cellular internalization • Use of well-characterized test materials in toxicity testing and evaluation of relevant physico-chemical properties
Prio 3: Appropriate control particles for toxicity testing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Suitable control materials to verify results from toxicity testing and to differentiate between general particle effects and specific MNP effects • Production and characterization of control particles and MNPs to allow comparison 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Development of methods and protocols including particle controls • Producing particle controls of high quality

<p>Prio 4: Assessing the joint effects of MNP and associated chemicals</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Relevance of leaching in different environmental and technical compartments; and the human body • Relevance of aging for leaching • Elucidate joint effects of MNP + chemicals • Prevention of cross-contamination of samples from laboratory equipment 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Development of quality-assured methods and protocols for leaching, inclusion of modelling approaches • Development of quality-assured methods and protocols to assess MNPs + chemicals fate in the human body • Methods and controls to prevent contamination during measurement • Effect-directed analysis
<p>Prio 5: characterise functional biomarkers</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • identify and characterize MNP-specific functional biomarkers • Cell-based assays selected based on the various human exposure routes 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • for detection of potential long-term effects of MNP • basis to build MNP specific AOPs and IATAs

Fig. 5: Based on the central figure from wish list manuscript [35]. For each step in risk assessment, the most crucial data gaps are summarized, as identified during PlasticsFatE.

4. Deviations from the Work plan

Major deviations from the working plan are addressed in the text above, the most important one relates to the realization that IATA formulation during PlasticsFatE will not be possible due to data and knowledge gaps. Alternatively, decision trees to facilitate IATA formulation in the future and a roadmap prioritising future MNP research are provided.

5. Performance of the partners

The deliverable was prepared by UFZ with contribution by UNILJ, UBT and STAMI.

6. Conclusions

During the 4 years of PlasticsFatE, scientists identified MNP in all environmental compartments and in all parts of the world. Also, MNPs have been found in almost all tissues and fluids of the human body (e.g. blood), pointing to the urge to come up with effective management strategies. This is underlined by the ongoing negotiations for an UN Global Plastics Treaty, where negotiators try to move away from plastic considered as only being a waste problem, which can be handled by better waste management. Further, it has been shown that plastic and associated chemicals affect humans and organisms in our environment, and effective risk assessment and management strategies need to be implemented. Hence, in this deliverable, we compiled the PlasticsFatE research activities and a concept for risk assessment in the form of decision trees. Despite many research activities across disciplines, we still experienced wide data and knowledge gaps. These are summarized and structured in a roadmap outlining future research activities needed to come to an effective risk assessment for MNP and associated chemicals.

Annex

Abbreviations & Glossary

AOP	Adverse Outcome Pathway
CLP	Classification Labelling and Packaging
CUSP	European research cluster to understand the health impacts of micro- and nanoplastics
Degradation	cleavage of the polymer backbone, four mechanisms: photodegradation, thermooxidative degradation, hydrolytic degradation and biodegradation by microorganisms
DSS	Decision support system
ECETOC	European Centre for Ecotoxicology and Toxicology of Chemicals
ECHA	European Chemicals Agency
EC50	Effective concentration showing 50 % effect
Fragmentation	following -> degradation, formation of small plastic particles from larger plastic items
IATA	<i>Integrated approaches to testing and assessment</i> , flexible approaches for chemical safety assessment based on the integration and translation of the data derived from multiple methods and sources (https://joint-research-centre.ec.europa.eu/eu-reference-laboratory-alternatives-animal-testing-eurl-ecvam/alternative-methods-toxicity-testing/iata-integrated-approaches-testing-and-assessment_en)
Leaching	process of chemicals being released from the polymer matrix into a surrounding liquid medium or solute
LDPE	Low density polyethylene
Monomer	(ancient Greek <i>monos</i> 'one', 'single' and <i>meros</i> 'part', 'portion'), a substance which, via the polymerization reaction, is converted into a repeating unit of the polymer sequence. (ECHA definition)
Microplastic	fragments of any type of plastic less than 5 mm in length, according to the U.S. National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration (NOAA) and the European Chemicals Agency. (Wikipedia, assessed 15 th Aug 2022, https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Microplastics)
Mn	Monomer
MNP	Micro and nanoplastic
MW	molecular weight
Nanoplastic	fragments of any type of plastic less than 1 µm (1000 nm) in length
NIAS	<i>non-intentionally added substances</i> , substances from various sources not added for technical reasons, subdivided into by-products, degradation products and contaminants (ECHA Guidance for monomers and polymers Version 2.0, 2012)
NOEL	No-observed effect level
OECD	Organisation of Economic Co-operation and Development
PBPK	Physiology-based pharmacokinetic model

Plastics	Plastics are a wide range of synthetic or semi-synthetic materials that use polymers as a main ingredient. (Wikipedia, assessed 15 th Aug 2022, https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Plastic)
Polymer	(from the ancient Greek polý 'much' and méros 'part', "built up from many (equal) parts"), a substance consisting of molecules characterised by the sequence of one or more types of monomer unit. Such molecules must be distributed over a range of molecular weights. Differences in the molecular weight are primarily attributable to differences in the number of monomer units. (ECHA definition)
PLC	Polymer of Low Concern
PMCDs	Prospective multi-criteria decision support system
PoC	Polymer of Concern
Primary microplastic	small pieces of plastic that are purposefully manufactured (Wikipedia, assessed 15 th Aug 2022, https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Microplastics)
PRR	Polymer requiring registration
PS	Polystyrene
RA	Risk assessment
REACH	Registration, Evaluation, Authorisation and Restriction of Chemicals
ROS	Reactive Oxygen Species
Secondary microplastic:	small pieces of plastic derived from the breakdown of larger plastic debris, both at sea and on land. (Wikipedia, assessed 15 th Aug 2022, https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Microplastics)
SSbD	Safe and sustainable by design
Weathering	-> Degradation due to chemical and physical changes caused by environmental stresses such as sunlight, heat, moisture, pollutants, mechanical stresses, and biological growth

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